

How does cited retracted reference influence the citing paper?

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Introduction

Retracted papers contain unreliable contents, and there have been many papers that were retracted for citing retracted works. Given the large number of citations to retracted papers, it can be inferred that there are many papers that should have been retracted (Cokol, M et al. 2007). However, the impact of retracted papers on the literature that cites it varies. Papers that have already been retracted due to citing retracted papers worth exploring, and research on their characteristics could be used as a tool for identifying problematic literature. Since science advances through existing knowledge, and accordingly, the more a paper depends on its cited retracted reference, the more the citing paper would be influenced. Full-text citation analysis method have been widely used to identify important citation and calculate the contribution of a citation. (Zhu et al. 2015; Wang et al. 2020). So, this study used full-text citation analysis method to assess the influence of cited retracted papers have on the citing papers.

Data and method

Definition

Figure 1 shows the relationship between different types of involved documents. The following is the meaning of these documents:

- (1) Retracted Papers (RP): papers that have been retracted;
- (2) Non-Retracted Papers (NRP): papers have not been retracted;
- (3) RP-test: RPs have been retracted for citing retracted works;
- (4) Target Retracted References (TRR): RPs have been cited by RP-test.
- (5) NRP-test: papers cited TRR, but have not been retracted yet.

Figure 1. Relationship between involved literature types

Data

The data for this study are collected from the Retraction Watch Database and the Web of Science (WOS) Database.

Figure 2. Data acquisition process.

As we can see in the Figure 2, that were labelled with the only one retraction reason “cites retracted work” in Retraction Watch, which represents a paper retracted for citing retracted paper. That is because we want to eliminate the influence of other reasons for retractions on the citing papers. In addition, for eliminating the impact of different retracted references on the citing papers, we choose the papers that have cited the same PRs (TRR) as NRPs.

Features

Zhu et al. (2015) have researched the effectiveness of a variety of features for determining the academic influence of a citation. The result indicates count_based feature, similarity_based features and position_based features play more important roles than other features. Wang et al. (2020) selected total citation length and number of neutral citations besides the three kinds of features. And in the procedure of processing the data, we find other features that may influence the citing papers: document types, citations method and self_citation. Based on these findings, we select the following 9 features to study how citing RPs influence the citing papers. They are: F1-num/proportion of retracted references; F2-mentioned frequency of retracted references; F3-citation position; F4-citation similarity; F5-citation polarity; F6-citation sentence length; F7-document types of citing papers; F8-citation appearance mode: appear alone and appear

together; F9-self_citation.

Figure 3. Method roadmap.

Results and Discussion

Table 3 shows the correlation coefficients between the features and the retraction labels. As shown in Table 4, we use the chi-square test to test grouped features.

Table 3. Pearson's correlation coefficient between every feature and retraction.

Feature	Pearson
Num of RPs	0.020
Proportion of RPs in references	0.559
Mentioned Frequency	0.556
Citation Sentence Length	0.065
Citation Position	-0.253
Citation Similarity	0.234
Citation Polarity	0.132
Document Types of Citing Papers	-0.320
Citation Appearance Mode	-0.356
Self_citation	0.330

Table 4. Results of the chi-square test between every feature and retraction.

Feature	p-value
Citation Polarity	0.312
Document Types of Citing Papers	<0.01
Citation Appearance Mode	<0.01
Self_citation	0.01

The above results show that mentioned frequency, the proportion of RPs in the references, citation appearance mode, the citing papers' type and self_citation may play more important role than other features. In terms of mentioned frequency, if the citing papers mention the RPs more times, the cited RPs are more likely to be important references of the citing paper. Secondly, the higher the proportion of RPs in the references is, the higher the risk of the citing paper being retracted is. And the citation appearance mode of RPs and NRPs is different, too. RPs are more likely to cite RPs alone, but NRPs usually cite RPs and other reference together in one sentence, which implies that references that appear alone usually play more

important role than references that appear with other references. We also need pay attention to the citing papers' type and self_citation, too, if the citing papers is commentary/editorials and one of its authors is same to that of the cited paper's, the possibility of the citing paper being retracted will be higher.

From the results of this study, to some extent, citation behaviours and citation intention can be described by full-text citation analysis method, and can help us to judge how useful every reference is to the citing paper. Besides that, using full-text citation analysis method to assess the influence of cited retracted papers have on the citing paper is meaningful and promising. And it is worth making further study.

Limitations and Future Work

Although we have made a list of many possible features that may depict the influence cited retracted references having on citing papers, owing to the limited time, this research only primarily chose 9 features. In the future, we plan to discuss more features and use more data to analyse how cited retracted references impact the citing paper. In addition to using full-text citation analysis method to assess the influence of cited RPs on the citing papers, we also plan to combine reasons for retraction to make further study. Generally speaking, if retracted papers contain scientific errors, they will have worse effect on the citing papers. Besides, we also plan to apply this set of methods to calculate the risk of retraction after citing RPs to help journals and researchers to pay attention to questionable research as soon as possible.

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